

Table 2. Total annual irrigation costs/ha for rice utilizing different power sources, southwest Louisiana, 1982.

Well type	Annual irrigation costs (US\$)			
	Diesel	LP gas	Natural gas	Electricity
I	50.96	50.46	35.59	25.45
II	50.31	49.88	34.84	24.77
III	48.05	47.99	32.99	23.11

1,287.7 million liters, respectively — was based on a gross estimate of about 92 cm of irrigation water applied to rice fields throughout the growing season.

Total annual irrigation costs were estimated for different power sources (Table 2). Diesel and LP gas were the most expensive fuels. Electricity was the least expensive. □

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Soil and crop management

Urea supergranule for alternately wet and dry fields

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Efficiency of applied nitrogen fertilizer must be increased. Recent International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice studies proved that deep placing urea supergranules (USG) at low doses in rice increased nitrogen efficiency in most soils. We tested USG deep placement in fields that are continuously flooded and alternately wet and dry. Rice was planted late in a split-plot design with four replications on a silt loam soil (Aquic Hapludoll).

Deep point placement was superior to urea best split application under recom-

Effect of method of urea application, water management, and planting dates on yield of rice variety Jaya, Pantnagar, India, 1982 rainy season.

Management condition	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	USG	Urea
<i>Timely transplanting (at 25 days)</i>		
Flooding (0-5 cm water)	5.3 ^b	4.9 ^b
Alternate wetting and drying	4.6	4.3
<i>Late transplanting (at 50 days)</i>		
Flooding (0-5 cm water)	5.8	4.7
Alternate wetting and drying	4.6	4.2
Mean	5.1	4.5
LSD 5% USG as urea		0.3
CV		8%

^aUSG = deep point placement, urea = split broadcast. ^bBrown planthopper reduced yield about 15% in USG and 10% in urea treatment (estimate).

mended water management (0 to 5 cm flooding) for timely and late planting. However, brown planthopper damage to the timely crop reduced the advantage of deep placed USG over broadcast urea.

When fields were intermittently wet

and dry, rice yield was reduced for both fertilizer application methods. In this experiment, deep placement of USG had no advantage over broadcast application in alternatively wet and dry fields (see table). Work on this subject is continuing.

Integrating brackish water aquaculture with rice cultivation on coastal saline soils

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Only one rice crop, usually during kharif, is grown in areas with coastal saline soils in India. Land usually remains fallow for the rest of the year because of high soil salinity and lack of good irrigation water. We studied the efficiency of short-term brackish water aquaculture during the

summer fallow assisted by saline tidal water from nearby estuaries and its effect on the yield of the subsequent kharif rice crop. Possible freshwater aquaculture was also studied.

We used two 0.01 5-ha rice plots at the RRS, CSSRI, Canning, on a low-lying coastal area of West Bengal. In Apr 1982 rice plots were filled with saline tidal water from the nearby river using a sluice gate. Brackish water aquaculture of tiger prawn (*P. monodon*) and mullet (*L. parsia*) was managed for 86 d, until Jun 1982. Aquaculture yielded an average 0.65 t of fish and prawn/ha (see table). Water salinity of the culture system varied from 12.5 to 40.0 mmho/cm, which increased soil salinity from 7.8 mmho/cm

Salinity cycle in brackish water rice and fish culture system.